

(Re)examining the correct names of five common mushrooms in South China

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Text

Five common mushrooms in South China, including four previously recognized as *Amanita* cf. *praegraveolens* (臭味鹅膏), *Macrocybe gigantea* (巨大口蘑), *Phallus rugulosus* (细皱鬼笔) and *Ranadivia modesta* (谦逊兰氏孔菌) (= *Trametes modesta* (谦逊栓孔菌)), and one previously having no reports, are here examined with molecular phylogenetic analyses by the Maximum Likelihood method following Yang *et al.* (2024) and discussed. Based on the results, correct names for the previously recognized *Amanita* cf. *praegraveolens* should be *Saproamanita manicata* (密鳞腐生鹅膏), for *M. gigantea* should be *M. crassa* (粗柄大口蘑), for *P. rugulosus* should be "*Satyros rugulosus* (细皱红鬼笔)", and for *Ranadivia modesta* should be "*Rhodofomitopsis rubida* (淡红拟层孔菌)"; *Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus* (巴基斯坦黏皮伞) is found to be a common species on urban green belts in South China cities, new to China.

Macrocybe crassa (Sacc.) Pegler & Lodge, in Pegler, Lodge & Nakasone, *Mycologia* 90(3): 497 (1998) (粗柄大口蘑) (Figures 1–2, Table 1, Supplement 1)
= *Tricholoma crassum* Sacc., *Sylloge Fungorum* 5: 109 (1887) (Replaced synonym: *Agaricus crassus* Berk., *London Journal of Botany* 6: 483 (1847), non *Agaricus crassus* Scop., *Flora Carniolica Edn 2 (Wien)* 2: 442 (1772))
= *Tricholoma giganteum* Masee, *Bulletin of Miscellaneous Informations of the Royal Botanical Gardens Kew*: 254 (1912)
= *Macrocybe gigantea* (Masee) Pegler & Lodge, in Pegler, Lodge & Nakasone, *Mycologia* 90(3): 497 (1998)

Notes: *Macrocybe crassa* and *M. gigantea* are, respectively, originally described from two locations close to each other, Sri Lanka and India. Both species are similar to each other and can be distinguished by the color of pileus, lamellae and stipe squamules and the shape of stipe in morphology, but are undistinguishable and suggested as

conspecific in phylogeny (Pegler *et al.* 1998, Vizzini *et al.* 2020; Figure 2). *Macrocybe crassa* in this case should be used on account of its priority, and could be a record new to China. Interestingly, only by morphological characteristics it still seems *M. crassa* is better for this species in South China, because at least the pale lamellae and the “off-white” stipe with “brown fibrillose streaks”, frequently observed from our collections, are indeed characteristics for *M. crassa* (Pegler *et al.* 1998).

As we observed (and practiced), this species is frequently gathered and consumed by the citizens in South China cities. In South China Agricultural University, researchers are not only studying its cultivation, even also exploring amazing ways to consume it (e.g. Liang & Mo 2016). However, although this species is considered edible without any special concerns in China, it may contain cyanide in basidiomata, possibly with a level of 86–283 $\mu\text{g/g}$ as measured by Shindo *et al.* (1999) under the name “*Tricholoma giganteum*” (from 11 samples bought from markets, see the original report for detailed conditions; We may make mistakes on explaining these because we are not familiar with Japanese language). The same authors claimed that “The level of residual cyanide in *T. giganteum* after cooking might be sufficient to cause poisoning with symptoms such as vomiting”. It looks true, as suggested by mushroom poisoning cases possible by *M. crassa* reported in China (Yang *et al.* 2024) and in Thailand (Nooron *et al.* 2023), but it could also be heavily relied on the born constitution ranging from one to another person, because we have eaten *M. crassa* several times, in large amount and even in a poorly cooked condition, however, have not experienced any troubles. Anyway, for others we will say, as concluded by Peiris *et al.* (2024)—“These mushrooms should never be consumed raw, and thorough cooking is recommended.”

Macrocybe lobayensis (R. Heim) Pegler & Lodge, originally described from Africa, is also sometimes applied to South China collections. However, the real position of this species is still uncertain due to the lack of credible sequence data. Its morphology described by Pegler *et al.* (1998) also looks distinct from *M. crassa* by, at least, the pileus “sometimes spotted ochre or red”.

Collections sequenced here: China, Guangdong Province, Guangzhou City, Jia Y. Lin, Kun L. Yang, Zhao-Rui Zhang & Zheng-Yue Lin: K2383 (HTBM0598), K23134 (HTBM0649) and L23256 (HTBM1208); Foshan City, kindly donated by net friends: S2346 (HTBM0289); Shenzhen City, Zhen-Xing Yao: S2347 (HTBM0290); Zhejiang Province, Taizhou City, kindly donated by net friends: S23194 (HTBM0437).

▲ **Figure 1.** *Macrocybe crassa* (Lower-rights: cooked, even made as mochi; photos by Kun L. Yang & Jia Y. Lin).

▲ **Figure 2.** Phylogeny of *Macrocybe crassa* and its allies inferred from ITS-nrLSU alignment, visualized with iTOL. Branches are annotated if supported by $\geq 50\%$ MLB. Collections sequenced in this study are highlighted in red. Holotypes are indicated by HT.

▼ **Table 1.** Information of the collections used in the phylogenetic analyses for *Macrocybe crassa* and its allies. Accession numbers are for Genbank. Collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes are indicated by HT.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	nrLSU	References
Ingroup						
<i>Macrocybe</i>	<i>M. crassa</i>	SFSU024256	Thailand	MN017540	MN017480	Vizzini <i>et al.</i> 2020
	<i>M. crassa</i>	KUBOT-KRMK-2020-10	India	MT883354	MT883286	Direct submission by Kantharaja & Krishnappa
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM0289	China	PV248371	PV243900	This study
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM0290	China	PV248380	-	This study
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM0437	China	PV248379	PV243898	This study
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM0598	China	PV248367	PV243891	This study
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM0649	China	PV248374	PV243890	This study
	<i>M. crassa</i>	HTBM1208	China	PV248368	PV243896	This study
	" <i>M. gigantea</i> "	SCAU3-12	China	OM716809	-	Direct submission by Hou
	<i>M. sardoa</i>	MCVE29083 (HT)	Italy	MN017542	MN017481	Vizzini <i>et al.</i> 2020
	<i>M. sardoa</i>	KUBOT-KRMK-2020-01	India	MT880333	MT879639	Direct submission by Kantharaja & Krishnappa
	<i>M. titans</i>	JBSD127429	Dominican Republic	MN017547	MN017486	Vizzini <i>et al.</i> 2020
<i>M. titans</i>	FLAS-F-59217	USA	MN017546	MN017485	Vizzini <i>et al.</i> 2020	
Outgroup						
<i>Anupama</i>	<i>A. indica</i>	CAL1725 (HT)	India	MH989587	MH989583	Raj <i>et al.</i> 2019

Rhodofomitopsis rubida (Berk.) Nom. ined. (淡红拟层孔菌) (Figures 3–4, Table 2, Supplement 2)

≡ *Polyporus rubidus* Berk., *London Journal of Botany* 6: 500 (1847)

≡ *Fomitopsis rubida* (Berk.) A. Roy & A.B. De [as "*rubidus*"], *Mycotaxon* 60: 317 (1996)

Notes: The boundary of *Fomitopsis* P. Karst. is in a controversy (Liu *et al.* 2023, Spirin *et al.* 2024), focusing on the issue of recognizing either a broad *Fomitopsis* s. l. or tens of microgenera with at least fifteen to be monotypic. We understand the solid and careful arguments on morphological concepts by Spirin *et al.* (2024), but we still prefer a treatment allow for more phylogenetic information in names of basic taxonomic ranks, and thus we adopt *Rhodofomitopsis* Cui *et al.* instead of *Fomitopsis* P. Karst. for

Polyporus rubidus Berk.

This species is originally described from Sri Lanka (Berkeley 1847), and our collections clustered with a toptype of it in the phylogeny (Figure 4). It is common in South China, and has been recognized as *Ranadivia modesta* (Kunze ex Fr.) Zmitr. (\equiv *Trametes modesta* (Kunze ex Fr.) Ryvarden) for a long time (e.g. Wu *et al.* 2011). However, true "*Ranadivia modesta*" possibly does not have a distribution in China, and as *Ranadivia* Zmitr. is currently synonymized with *Daedalea* Pers. s. str., "*Ranadivia modesta*" is better to be called with the name *Daedalea modesta* (Kunze ex Fr.) Aoshima.

Collections sequenced here: China, Guangdong Province, Guangzhou City, Jia Y. Lin, Kun L. Yang & Zhen-Chao Liu: L23145 (HTBM1097), L23238 (HTBM1190) and S23549 (HTBM1660).

▲ **Figure 3.** *Rhodofomitopsis rubida* (photos by Kun L. Yang & Jia Y. Lin).

▲ **Figure 4.** Phylogeny of *Rhodofomitopsis rubida* and its allies inferred from ITS alignment, visualized with iTOL. Branches are annotated if supported by $\geq 50\%$ MLB. Collections sequenced in this study are highlighted in red.

▼ **Table 2.** Information of the collections used in the phylogenetic analyses for *Rhodofomitopsis rubida* and its allies. Accession numbers are for Genbank. Collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. (*) Nom. ined.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	References
<i>Rhodofomitopsis</i>	<i>R. africana</i>	Cui16362	Vietnam	ON417189	Liu <i>et al.</i> 2023
	<i>R. cupreorosea</i>	CBS236.87	Costa Rica	DQ491400	Kim <i>et al.</i> 2007
	<i>R. feei</i>	Ryvardeen37603	Venezuela	KC844850	Han <i>et al.</i> 2015
	<i>R. lilacinogilva</i>	Schigel5193	Australia	KR605773	Han <i>et al.</i> 2016
	<i>R. monomitica</i>	Dai10630	China	KY421732	Chen & Wu 2017
	<i>R. oleracea</i>	MD177	USA	KC585296	Ortiz-Santana <i>et al.</i> 2013
	* <i>R. rubida</i>	UOC MINNP M18	Sri Lanka	KP780437	Direct submission by Ediriweera <i>et al.</i> , Spirin <i>et al.</i> 2024
	*<i>R. rubida</i>	HTBM1097	China	PV248377	This study
	*<i>R. rubida</i>	HTBM1190	China	PV248378	This study
	*<i>R. rubida</i>	HTBM1660	China	PV248381	This study
" <i>Fomitopsis</i> "	" <i>Fo. carnea</i> "	Otto Miettinen 13120	Indonesia	KC595916	Ortiz-Santana <i>et al.</i> 2013
	" <i>Fo. eucalypti</i> "	Cui16773	Australia	MW377281	Direct submission by Liu & Cui
<i>Flavidoporia</i>	<i>Fl. pulvinascens</i>	Cui9542	China	MG787589	Liu <i>et al.</i> 2023

Saproamanita manicata (Berk. & Broome) Redhead, Vizzini, Drehmel & Contu, *IMA Fungus* 7(1): 123 (2016) (密鳞腐生鹅膏) (Figures 5–6, Table 3, Supplement 3)

Notes: This species is originally described from Sri Lanka (Berkeley & Broome 1871). The first time that we noticed it was on September 13, 2020, along a construction site in Guangzhou City, and later we found it quite common across the urban green belts in this city. Sometimes it forms large fairy rings on broad bare lands, clearly suggesting it a saprotroph (Figure 5). After damaged its basidiomata excrete hyaline liquids fast and distinct, behaving like a *Lactarius* species but with hyaline latex, and thus we think it has hydroplerous hyphae present in context. Its basidiomata are also distinct in having a quite rancid smell, can easily make a room no longer suitable to live in when storing its collections on drying. The first time that we knew its correct name was in 2021, after sending a collection to Dr. Qing Cai for sequencing (Grateful to her help!). *Saproamanita manicata* could be a species new to China, but the first description of it in China is actually made in Yang (2015: 108), under the name *Amanita* cf. *praegraveolens*, reported from lawns in Taiwan Province.

On June 28, 2023, a mushroom poisoning incident from Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region happened. A photo of the mushrooms eaten by the patient was sent to an Internet group with me, clearly showing a mass of *Saproamanita manicata* basidiomata. Soon I commented the name of this fungus for reference, and finally this incident was recorded in the report by Dr. Hai-jiao Li *et al.* (2024). More details regarding the poisoning reactions were unclear.

Whether *Amanita* s. l. should be split into more genera is suffering from a bitter controversy (Redhead *et al.* 2016, Tulloss *et al.* 2016, Cui *et al.* 2018). Similar to the explanation in *Rhodofomitopsis*, we prefer a treatment allow for more phylogenetic information in names of basic taxonomic ranks, specifically, in the generic names in this case. Through the great efforts leading by Dr. Zhu L. Yang, the 11 sections now recognized within *Amanita* s. l., namely sect. *Amanita*, sect. *Amarrendiae*, sect. *Caesareae*, sect. *Vaginatae*, sect. *Amidella*, sect. *Arenariae*, sect. *Phalloideae*, sect. *Roanokenses*, sect. *Strobiliformes*, sect. *Validae* and sect. *Lepidella*, are obviously representing unique groups each on a higher level during evolution, well characterized in morphological,

ecological and phylogenetical (including “phylogenomical” (Cai *et al.* 2024; *Amanita arenaria* misidentified?)) senses. Being persons having not been deeply worked with Amanitaceae, it is impolite and unfair for us to intervene further issues regarding this group, so we do only accept the ready-made *Saproamanita* Redhead *et al.* and the rest still *Amanita*, although there are also usable generic names previously made for many other sections (Figure 6).

Collections sequenced here: China, Guangdong Province, Guangzhou City, Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhao-Rui Zhang: K2385 (HTBM0600) and K2387 (HTBM0602).

▲ **Figure 5.** *Saproamanita manicata* (photos by Kun L. Yang).

▲ **Figure 6.** Phylogeny of *Saproamanita manicata*, *Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus* and their allies inferred from ITS-nrLSU alignment, visualized with iTOL. Branches are annotated if supported by $\geq 50\%$ MLB. Collections sequenced in this study are highlighted in red. Holotypes are indicated by HT.

▼ **Table 3.** Information of the collections used in the phylogenetic analyses for *Saproamanita manicata*, *Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus* and their allies. Accession numbers are for Genbank. Collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes are indicated by HT. (*) Nom. ined.

Higher taxa	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	nrLSU	References
Ingroup						
sect. <i>Amanita</i>	<i>A. muscaria</i>	HMJAU4549	Russia	MH508440	KR824787	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
(<i>Amanita</i> s. str.)	<i>A. farinosa</i>	HKAS100490	China	MH508339	MH486495	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Amarrendiae</i>	<i>X. pseudoinculta</i>	PERTH08105731	Australia	-	MH486770	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
(<i>Amarrendia</i>)	<i>X. morenoi</i>	MES1588	Chile	-	KY053383	Truong <i>et al.</i> 2017
sect. <i>Amidella</i>	<i>X. pinophila</i>	HKAS68307	China	MH508503	MH486758	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
(<i>Amidella</i>)	<i>X. rufobrunnescens</i>	GDGM42374	China	-	KT865210	Deng <i>et al.</i> 2016
sect. <i>Arenariae</i>	<i>X. arenaria</i>	VPI679	Australia	-	GQ925382	Justo <i>et al.</i> 2010
sect. <i>Caesareae</i>	<i>X. rubroflava</i>	HKAS83089	China	MH508568	MH486827	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
(<i>Torrendia</i>)	<i>X. imazekii</i>	HKAS71045	Japan	MH508397	MH486591	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Lepidella</i>	<i>X. flavofloccosa</i>	HKAS90174	China	MH508352	KT833801	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
(<i>Saproamanita</i>)	<i>X. manicata</i>	PDD88353	New Zealand	-	MH486638	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>X. manicata</i>	HTBM0600	China	PV248375	PV243892	This study
	<i>X. manicata</i>	HTBM0602	China	PV248376	PV243893	This study

... continued below

▼ **Table 3.** (continued)

Higher taxa	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	nrLSU	References
	<i>*X. galerum-gandalfii</i>	PDD93780	New Zealand	-	HQ539742	Direct submission by Tulloss <i>et al.</i>
	<i>X. vittadinii</i>	HKAS101430	Italy	MH508651	MH486950	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Phalloideae</i>	<i>X. exitialis</i>	HKAS75776	China	JX998025	JX998051	Cai <i>et al.</i> 2012
(<i>Amanitina</i>)	<i>X. franzii</i>	HKAS77321	China	MH508357	KJ466481	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Roanokenses</i>	<i>X. gymnopus</i>	HKAS71618	China	MH508393	MH486582	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>X. kotohiraensis</i>	HKAS100500	China	MH508414	MH486613	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Strobiliformes</i>	<i>X. strobiliformis</i>	MB-001177	Germany	MH508614	MH486895	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>X. cinereoradicata</i>	HKAS101435	China	MH508307	MH486451	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Vaginatae</i>	<i>X. griseofolia</i>	HKAS38159	China	AY436448	AY436488	Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2004
(<i>Amanitopsis</i>)	<i>X. liquii</i>	HKAS58800	China	MH508425	MH486626	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
sect. <i>Validae</i>	<i>X. fritillaria</i>	HKAS80227	China	MH508365	MH486543	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>X. rubescens</i>	HKAS92034	China	MH508558	MH486815	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
Outgroup						
<i>Zhuliangomyces</i>	<i>Z. illinitus</i>	HKAS90168	China	MH508659	KT833814	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>Z. ochraceoluteus</i>	MEL2305332	Australia	MH508660	MH486965	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>Z. olivaceus</i>	HKAS101960	China	MH561739	MH561738	Cui <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>Z. pakistanicus</i>	LAH35337 (HT)	Pakistan	MN240881	-	Usman & Khalid 2020
	<i>Z. pakistanicus</i>	HTBM0409	China	PV248369	PV243897	This study
	<i>Z. pakistanicus</i>	HTBM0478	China	PV248370	PV243899	This study

Satyrus rugulosus (E. Fisch.) Nom. ined. (细皱红鬼笔) (Figures 7–8, Table 4, Supplement 4)
 ≡ *Ithyphallus rugulosus* E. Fisch., *Annales du Jardin Botanique de Buitenzorg* 6: 35 (1887)
 ≡ *Phallus rugulosus* (E. Fisch.) Lloyd, *Mycological Writings (Cincinnati)* 2(31): 402 (1908)

Notes: Analysed with a broader outgroup, the well-known *Phallus rubicundus* (Bosc) Fr. complex, characterized by reddish basidiomata with a rugose pileus surface, appear to be separated from *Phallus Junius* ex L. s. str. and sister to the head-veiled genus *Itajahya* Möller (Figure 8). Therefore, the generic name *Satyrus* Bosc erected for *Phallus rubicundus* seems better for the recently accepted *Phallus rugulosus* (E. Fisch.) Lloyd.

Collections sequenced here: China, Guangdong Province, Guangzhou City, Kun L. Yang & Jia Y. Lin: K2315 (HTBM0530) and K23151 (HTBM0666).

▲ **Figure 7.** *Satyrus rugulosus* (photos by Kun L. Yang).

▲ **Figure 8.** Phylogeny of *Satyrus rugulosus* and its allies inferred from ITS-nrLSU-*atp6* alignment, visualized with iTOL. Branches are annotated if supported by $\geq 50\%$ MLB. Collections sequenced in this study are highlighted in red. Holotypes and paratypes are indicated by HT and PT, respectively.

▼ **Table 4.** Information of the collections used in the phylogenetic analyses for *Satyrus rugulosus* and its allies. Accession numbers are for Genbank. Collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes and paratypes are indicated by HT and PT, respectively. (*) Nom. ined.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	nrLSU	<i>atp6</i>	References
Ingroup							
<i>Itajahya</i>	<i>I. rosea</i>	It	India	MN135577	MN134400	-	Direct submission by Kshirsagar & Borde
<i>Lysurus</i>	<i>I. galericulatus</i>	KSRF0014	India	MF506819	MH168327	MH175196	Direct submission by Rajput & Ravi
	<i>L. borealis</i>	OSC39531	-	-	DQ218641	DQ218929	Hosaka <i>et al.</i> 2006
	<i>L. cruciatus</i>	MLHC-296	Argentina	KY494890	KY494902	KY494877	Hernández Caffot <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>L. mokusin</i>	MB02012	-	-	DQ218507	DQ218791	Hosaka <i>et al.</i> 2006
<i>Mutinus</i>	<i>L. sphaerocephalum</i>	MLHC-232	Argentina	-	KY494900	KY494875	Hernández Caffot <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>M. albotruncatus</i>	UFRN-Fungos 2025 (HT)	Brazil	MF447826	KT183493	KT183490	Direct submission by Cabral <i>et al.</i> , Silva <i>et al.</i> 2015
	<i>M. bambusinus</i>	KH-TBG11-449	Japan	MF447820	-	KF783263	Direct submission by Cabral <i>et al.</i> , Trierveiler-Pereira <i>et al.</i> 2014
	<i>M. caninus</i>	RE21118	-	MF447827	-	-	Direct submission by Cabral <i>et al.</i>

... continued below

▼ **Table 4.** (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	ITS	nrLSU	<i>atp6</i>	References
	<i>M. elegans</i>	KUO_05170701_IL	USA	-	MK602337	-	Direct submission by Kuo <i>et al.</i>
	<i>M. fleischeri</i>	INPA240012	-	MF447828	KT183495	-	Direct submission by Cabral <i>et al.</i> , Silva <i>et al.</i> 2015
	<i>M. verrucosus</i>	UFRN-Fungos 2803 (PT)	Brazil	MF447810	MF447808	-	Direct submission by Cabral <i>et al.</i> , Crous <i>et al.</i> 2017
<i>Phallus</i>	<i>P. atrovolvatus</i>	INPA240016	-	MG678531	MG678470	MG678559	Cabral <i>et al.</i> 2019
	<i>P. cinnabarinus</i>	INPA255835	-	KJ764821	MG678471	MG678561	Cabral <i>et al.</i> 2019
	<i>P. denigricans</i>	INPA272383	-	MG678486	MG678455	MG678541	Cabral <i>et al.</i> 2019
	<i>P. echinovolvatus</i>	TNS-F-34480	Thailand	MF372137	MF372129	-	Trierveiler-Pereira <i>et al.</i> 2017
	<i>P. hadriani</i>	KH11092003-1	-	DQ404385	AY885165	-	Direct submission by Matheny <i>et al.</i>
	<i>P. indusiatus</i>	INPA264930	-	MG678499	MG678462	MG678549	Cabral <i>et al.</i> 2019
	<i>P. luteus</i>	GDGM26326	China	MT261850	MT261793	-	Direct submission by Li
	<i>P. multicolor</i>	MEL1054289	-	-	DQ218628	DQ218918	Hosaka <i>et al.</i> 2006
	<i>P. purpurascens</i>	SINOP26	-	MG678488	MG678457	MG678543	Cabral <i>et al.</i> 2019
	<i>P. ultraduplicatus</i>	HMAS253050 (HT)	China	KJ591584	KJ591586	-	Adamčík <i>et al.</i> 2015
<i>Satyrium</i>	* <i>S. rugulosus</i>	TNS-F-46049	China	MF372142	MF372134	-	Trierveiler-Pereira <i>et al.</i> 2017
	* <i>S. rugulosus</i>	GDGM73550	China	MT361865	MT261859	-	Direct submission by Li
	" <i>S. rubicundus</i> "	MA-Fungi-64695	Spain	MT947732	-	MT949878	Melanda <i>et al.</i> 2021
	* <i>S. rugulosus</i>	HTBM0530	China	PV248372	PV243888	-	This study
	* <i>S. rugulosus</i>	HTBM0666	China	PV248373	PV243889	-	This study
	<i>S. rubicundus</i>	CLO3220	USA	-	MK652718	-	Li <i>et al.</i> 2020
	<i>S. rubicundus</i>	OLO4186	USA	-	MK652719	-	Li <i>et al.</i> 2020
	<i>S. rubicundus</i>	KUO05071201	USA	-	MK652721	-	Li <i>et al.</i> 2020
<i>Xylophallus</i>	<i>X. clavatus</i>	USJ-28095	-	-	MH020744	-	Direct submission by Cabral, Crous <i>et al.</i> 2018
	<i>X. xylogenus</i>	CJL-120214-08	French Guiana	-	KF783252	-	Trierveiler-Pereira <i>et al.</i> 2014
Outgroup							
<i>Gastrosporum</i>	<i>G. gossypinum</i>	TNS-F-79676	Japan	MN954700	MN954696	-	Kasuya <i>et al.</i> 2020
	<i>G. simplex</i>	S-F21795	Spain	-	KF783242	KF783258	Trierveiler-Pereira <i>et al.</i> 2014

Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus Usman & Khalid, *Phytotaxa* 443(2): 202 (2020) (巴基斯坦黏皮伞) (Figures 6 and 9, Table 3, Supplement 3)

Notes: The first time that we noticed this species was on June 10, 2022, in an urban green belt in Guangzhou City (Figure 9), and soon we sent this collection to Dr. Qing Cai for sequencing and knew its name (Grateful to her help!). Later, we noticed that citizens from other South China cities also found this species as shown in their photos posted on Internet groups and then we requested them to gather collections for us. With sequence evidence, absolutely they are the same species.

As suggested by the epithet, this species is originally described from Pakistan (Usman & Khalid 2020), and is new to China. It gives us a surprise that *Zhuliangomyces* species, although usually considered rare and temperate-distributed, could be common on urban green belts in South China cities.

Collections sequenced here: China, Guangdong Province, Shenzhen City, Zhen-Xing Yao: S23166 (HTBM0409); Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Nanning City, Yu-Chi Cai, S23235 (HTBM0478).

▲ **Figure 9.** *Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus* (photos by Kun L. Yang).

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Availability of data and materials

The sequences generated in this study are available in GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>) with the accession numbers shown in Tables 1–4. The collections studied in this study were deposited in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM). Supplementary materials were deposited in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) with doi 10.5281/zenodo.15005715, including the following items: (Supplement 1) The concatenated ITS-nrLSU alignment used for the phylogenetic analysis of *Macrocybe crassa* and its allies, arranged in order of ITS-nrLSU; (Supplement 2) The ITS alignment used for the phylogenetic analysis of *Rhodofomitopsis rubida* and its allies; (Supplement 3) The concatenated ITS-nrLSU alignment used for the phylogenetic analysis of *Saproamanita manicata*, *Zhuliangomyces pakistanicus* and their allies, arranged in order of ITS-nrLSU; (Supplement 4) The concatenated ITS-nrLSU-*atp6* alignment used for the phylogenetic analysis of *Satyru rugulosus* and its allies, arranged in order of ITS-nrLSU-*atp6*.

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